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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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B2(RIBOFLAVIN) VITAMININI SANOATDA ISHLAB CHIQRILISHI

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Annotatsiya: Vitaminlar organizmning normal faoliyati uchun zarur bo'lgan, lekin organizmda ishlab chiqarilmaydigan mikromaqsadli birikmalardir. Ular turli biologik jarayonlarni boshqarishda, immun tizimi, asab tizimi va energiya almashinuvini qo'llab-quvvatlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Vitaminlarni an'anaviy usullar bilan ishlab chiqarish o'zining murakkabligi va iqtisodiy jihatdan samarasizligi sababli, so'nggi yillarda biotexnologik usullar orqali ishlab chiqarish tez rivojlanib bormoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: Vitamin, avitaminoz, gipovitaminoz, gipervitaminoz, *Ashbya gossypii*, *Candida famata*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*.

Vitaminlar (lotincha: vita - hayot), darmon dori - tirik organizmning hayot faoliyati va normal moddalar almashinuvi uchun zarur bo'lgan organik birikmalar. Vitaminlar oziq-ovqat tarkibida uchraydigan oziqa omillari jumlasiga kirib, organizmda sodir bo'ladigan moddalar almashinuvining boshqarilishida ishtirok etish orqali biokimyoviy va fiziologik jarayonlarni me'yoriy chegarada kechishini ta'minlaydigan moddalardir. Bu moddalar organizm uchun juda ham oz miqdorda talab qilinishi bilan birga, organizmning ular bilan ta'minlanishiga bevosita bog'liq bo'lgan avitaminoz, gipovitaminoz va gipervitaminoz holatlari ham uchrab turadi[1]. Vitaminlar fizik, kimyoviy tuzilishi jihatidan ikki guruhga bo'linadi. Suvda eriydigan vitaminlar: vitamin B majmuasi, C, vitamin P va boshqalar. Yog'da eriydigan vitaminlar: vitamin A, D, E, K. Vitaminlarni biotexnologik ishlab chiqarish — bu zamonaviy biologik texnologiyalar yordamida vitaminlar ishlab chiqarish jarayoni bo'lib, u mikroorganizmlar, o'simliklar yoki boshqa biologik tizimlar yordamida amalga oshiriladi. Bu jarayonlar sanoat miqyosida vitaminlar va ularning ishlab chiqarishining samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan[2,6].

Riboflavin ishlab chiqarish 15 yildan kamroq vaqt ichida kimyoviy sintezdan eksklyuziv biotexnologik sintezga o'tdi. Kimyoviy sintez taxminan 50 yil davomida riboflavin ishlab chiqarishning asosiy usuli bo'lib kelgan. Shunga qaramay, murakkab sintez jarayoni, nisbatan yuqori narx va yuqori ifloslanish xavfi tufayli fermentatsiya usuli kabi kimyoviy sintezning muqobil usullari rivojlana boshladi va oxir-oqibat riboflavin ishlab chiqarishning asosiy usullariga aylandi. Hozirgi vaqtda sanoat riboflavin ishlab chiqarishda uch turdagi shtammlar qo'llaniladi: *Ashbya gossypii*, *Candida famata* va *Bacillus subtilis*. Bundan tashqari, *Escherichia coli* va *Lactobacillus* bo'yicha ko'plab so'nggi tadqiqotlar o'tkazildi. Riboflavinning fermentativ ishlab chiqarilishi amalga oshiriladi suv osti kulturalardan foydalaniladi. Mikrob shtamidan riboflavin ishlab chiqarish fermentatsiyasiga uglerod manbai,

minerallar va pH kabi omillar ta'sir qiladi. Fermentatsiya genetik muhandislik texnologiyasidan foydalangan holda riboflavin hosilini oshiradi, bu shtammda riboflavin ishlab chiqarishni o'zgartirish va qo'zg'atish, shuningdek, purin yo'li va pentoza fosfat yo'lining (PP yo'li) metabolik oqimini tartibga solish va shu bilan fermentatsiya jarayonini optimallashtiradi[3,4]. Bitta riboflavin molekulasining biosintezi uchun substrat sifatida bir molekula guanozin triptofosfat (GTP) va ikkita ribuloza 5-fosfat molekulasini kerak bo'ladi. GTP ning imidazol halqasi gidrolitik tarzda ochilib, 4,5-diaminopirimidin hosil qiladi, u 5-amino-6-ribitilamino-2,4(1H,3H)-pirimidindionga deaminatsiya, yon zanjirning qisqarishi va fosforillanish ketma-ketligi bilan aylanadi. Ribuloza 5-fosfatdan olingan 5-amino-6-ribitilamino-2,4-pirimidindionning 3,4-dihidroksi-2-butanon 4-fosfat bilan kondensatsiyasi 6,7-dimetil-8-ribitillumazinni hosil qiladi. Lumazin hosilasining dismutatsiyasi natijasida riboflavin va 5-amino-6-ribitilamino-2,4-pirimidindion hosil bo'ladi, ular biosintetik yo'lda qayta ishlanadi[5,7].

1-rasm. B2(riboflavin) vitaminini sanoatda ishlab chiqarilish texnologik chizmasi

Xulosa: Riboflavin biosintezi murakkab biokimyoviy jarayon bo'lib, unda bir nechta fermentativ bosqichlar mavjud. Genetik muhandislik orqali riboflavin ishlab chiqarishning samaradorligi va miqdori oshirilgan. Fermentatsiya jarayonini optimallashtirishda metabolik yo'llarning tartibga solinishi muhim rol o'ynaydi. Bu texnologiyalar sanoat miqyosida vitamin ishlab chiqarishning samaradorligini yanada oshirishga yordam bermoqda. Riboflavin ishlab chiqarishning biotexnologik usullari nafaqat iqtisodiy samarali, balki ekologik jihatdan ham foydalidir.

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